

Movie Watching Preferences and Patterns: A Survey of the Female Students in the University of Sindh, Jamshoro, Pakistan

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Abstract

Movies are one of the media which are significant sources of entertainment, information, and education for the masses. People in every part of the world perceive movies as a type of entertainment or a way to have fun. These are critical media for the masses to be entertained through. People of all ages, especially youth inclusive of females are much interested in watching movies. According to previous studies, Females watch movies of genres like fantasy, adventure, sci-fi, etc. other than romantic movies, and now Females like to watch action movies. The purpose of this study is to analyze the preferences and patterns of movie watching by female students at the University of Sindh, Jamshoro. For data collection, a cross-sectional survey was conducted by applying a purposive sampling technique. The findings revealed that female students watched movies of various genres; they mostly watched movies on mobile. Further, it was found that most of the female students watched movies just for entertainment purposes.

Keywords: *Movie Watching Preferences, Sindh University Female Students, Watching Patterns.*

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Introduction

Movies, also known as films, are a type of visual communication that uses moving pictures and sound to tell stories or teach people something significant. These are some of the media which are significant sources of entertainment, information, and education for the masses (Baiju, 2019; Lehman & Luhr, 2018). People in every part of the world perceive movies as a type of entertainment or a way to have fun. According to Ságvári (2009), in modern societies, movies and cinemas play a vital role for all generations, especially for the younger generation. Whereas, Diefendorff and Chandler (2011) added that movies leave their impact on people with particular effect on personality and specific behaviors (Ahmad, Shafi, & Shah, 2016). Additionally, Deák (2008) attempted in his study to explore the particular motives that can be satisfied by watching movies.

Different movies have different impacts on society. Comic, adventurous, biographical, and fantasy movies provide a positive impact. Such movies are just for entertainment and make audience laugh and be happy. However, other kinds of movies like action, thriller, and horror movies may put a negative impact on society. Bearden and Etzel (1982) believed that in the case of choosing brands and products, groups have identified their choices but in the case of movies the influence of the choices of groups need to be explored.

According to Hofmeister-Tóth and Töröcsik (1996), movie watching can be placed in both the visible and the invisible (or hidden) consumption groups. Consumer behavior is significantly affected by their immediate environment. Zoltán and Lakatos (2011) put forth that movies have significant influences on minds, which in turn directly relate to the psychological behavior of individuals. When one is not able to fulfil his needs via legal means, he would resort towards the free sources or maybe illegal means to download pirated movies for the fulfilment of his psychological needs.

Today's generation, inclusive of females, is much interested in watching movies. Other than romantic movies, females watch genres like fantasy, adventure, sci-fic and action movies. All these movies leave different impacts on Females, are nowadays very passionate about feminism-based movies like Sofia, Brave, etc. and because of these movies' females become feminists, and because of the fantasy movies, many Females want to live their life like a princess.

Movies also impact Females' emotions and feelings. The general assumption in media production is that males and females enjoy different types of films, and this can be supported by genre and content satisfaction (Gantz & Wenner, 1991). For example, in a specific study (Fischhoff, Antonio, & Lewis, 1998), it was proposed that "women's films" are movies in which the story is told from the woman's point of view (e.g., "Muriel's Wedding"), or in which the story centres around women and women's issues is generally more popular. The review of literature revealed that there is a lack of studies regarding movie watching preferences and patterns in Pakistan. Thus, the purpose of this study is to analyze the preferences and patterns of movie watching by female students in the University of Sindh, Jamshoro.

Problem Statement

Movies are one of the critical mediums for the masses to be entertained through. People of all ages, especially youth, watch movies with profound interest. According to Horváth, Gyenge, and Rácz (2015), various influences and sources of information affect the choices of university students concerning both the methods of viewing movies and the selection of certain movies. Maxfield (2003) said that there are excellent relations between movie-viewing choice and movie stars, trailers, subject matter, and genre.

Universities play a vital role in society, and university students pose a potential target market for movie consumption. Female students of universities also watch movies with different patterns and preferences. In this way, this study aims to assess what kind of movies Female students in the University of Sindh, Jamshoro watch and what motivates them to choose a movie of their specific choice.

Moreover, it is assumed that female students of university mostly watch movies on mobile or laptops. Sometimes they also watch movies on television with the family. Added to this, there is also a trend among them that every weekend females want to watch movies at the cinema. Further, they prefer to watch fantasy, drama, and romantic movies. Whereas, some proportion of them also prefer to watch science fiction, horror, adventure, and action movies. Finally, Females mostly watch movies just for entertainment.

Research Objectives

- To know the movie-watching preferences among Female students in the UoS, Jamshoro
- To determine the movie watching patterns among Female students in the UoS, Jamshoro

Research Questions

RQ1: What are movie-watching preferences among Female students at the University of Sindh, Jamshoro?

RQ2: What are the movie-watching patterns among Female students at the University of Sindh, Jamshoro?

Literature Review

This research examines the movie watching patterns and preferences of Female students that how and what genres of movies they watch mostly. A movie or film is an image that creates an illusion of moving images on the screen. Movies are also a form of entertainment. Nowadays, movies are part of our society and culture; movie viewers have got so addicted that they cannot imagine their lives without watching movies.

Moreover, the term genre is applied to any category of literature or other forms of art or entertainment, e.g. music, whether spoken, audio, or visual-based

movies, etc. Whereas, the primary purpose of every genre is to entertain the audiences in a different style. In our society, as in many others when a new type comes, people forget the old ones. There are different genres of movies, e.g. Action, adventure, comedy, drama, fantasy, historical, horror, romantic, science fiction, etc. Various genres of movies have different impacts on society. Some movies are just for entertainment and make viewers laugh and happy; whereas other movies like action, thriller, and horror movies, leave a negative impact on society.

Bearden and Etzel (1982) believed that in the case of choosing brands and products groups have identified their choices but in the case of movies, to know the influence of the groups need to be identified. According to Hofmeister-Tóth and Törőcsik (1996), movie watching can be placed in both the visible and the invisible (or hidden) consumption groups. And consumer behavior is significantly affected by their immediate environment, especially those groups that one is, or would like to be a member.

Zoltán and Lakatos (2011) write that movies have a significant influence on minds, which directly relates to the psychological behavior of individuals. One might not be able to fulfill his needs via legal means. So, he would retreat towards the free sources or maybe illegal means to download the pirated movies for his psychological needs.

It could be referred to in some studies that people watch movies with different patterns and preferences. As some people watch movies at home with their family, and some people watch movies at the cinema with their friends. People usually watch drama and comedy movies with their families. However, with friends, they watch all types of movies. In the early ages, people mostly watched movies on television, but now they have other means to watch online on laptops and mobiles. According to Hofmeister Toth (2006), the main reason for this change in our society is people's behavior, affected by their choices.

Additionally, it is prevalent and natural that every person has his likes and dislikes in everything. Thus, every person likes to watch different genres of movies. Those people who are emotionally stable prefer to watch action, horror, and adventure movies. However, those who are emotionally weak and soft-hearted prefer to watch comedy, drama, and historical movies. Added in the context of movie watching purposes, some people watch movies just for entertainment; whereas, others watch movies to gain knowledge. Thus, the choice of various genres of movies to watch is also known as the movie-watching preferences of people.

Further, in this regard, Hirschman and Holbrook (1982) share that viewers' choices and preferences about the movie genres are naturally related to their sensations and emotions or aspects of any experience. Similarly, Zufryden (1996) also believed that the significance of genres or movie choice is identified as the need and preferences of the people.

Besides, in a pilot study, Horváth, Gyenge, and Rácz (2017) examined the movie viewing habits of university students. It focused on the diverse impacts on sources of information, which influence their selection and choices. It concluded that viewers get information about movie awards on pirated webs and some legal movie streaming services. Likewise, Horváth and Gyenge (2017), in a study of movie viewing habits of college and university students of Hungary concluded that for

movie selection, trailers are the main source of information for them. Most students visit the movie theatre with friends and significant others.

Also, Chen, Gao, and Rau (2017) in a survey of 248 participants regarding motives for watching or not watching Danmaku videos. The study concluded that participants watched Danmaku videos for information, entertainment, and social connectedness.

Research Method

In this quantitative study, a cross-sectional survey method was applied for data collection. Regarding this, Wiseman and Aron (1970) defined a survey as a highly structured research method to obtain information from a large number of respondents, who are presumed to be representative of a specific population. Welman, Kruger, and Mitchell (2005) also support that the survey approach allows collecting information from a larger sample, as opposed to interviews or other forms of data gathering. The quantitative research of the study was conducted with the aid of questionnaires. The survey instrument took between five to ten minutes to complete, contained only closed-ended questions, grouped into five sections, covering the respondent's movie viewing frequency, information gathering methods, movie viewing habits, attitudes, and demographics. The sample consisted of *female* students of Sindh University. SPSS software tool was used to analyze the data.

The population of this study was female students enrolled in Sindh University, Jamshoro. This University is one of the oldest universities in Pakistan. However, the targeted respondents that are a total of 100 were purposively sampled from the following five departments. That is the Department of Media & Communication Studies, the Department of Psychology, the Department of International Relations, the Department of English and the Department of Arts & Design, 20 participants each.

The data was collected with the help of a pre-designed questionnaire. That had two main parts, one for demographic variables of the respondents. Whereas, the other part of the questionnaire consisted of such questions which aimed to seek and gather opinions of the respondents about the movie watching patterns. Finally, the collected data were analyzed with descriptive statistics and were presented in tables for description.

Analysis and Results

Demographic Information

Table 1: *Demographic characteristic (continued)*

Variable	Frequency	Percent (%)
Name of department		
Media and Communication Studies	20	(20.0)
Psychology	20	(20.0)

International Relations	20	(20.0)
English	20	(20.0)
Arts and Design	20	(20.0)
Total	100	(100)
Age		
18 to 22	82	(82.0)
23 to 27	17	(17.0)
28 and Above	1	(1.0)
Total	100	(100)
Mother Tongue		
Sindhi	30	(30.0)
Urdu	48	(48.0)
Punjabi	13	(13.0)
Balochi	2	(2.0)
Pashto	1	(1.0)
Saraiki	6	(6.0)
Total	100	(100)
Parent's Occupation		
Government Employee	53	(53.0)
Personal Business	26	(26.0)
Unemployed	2	(2.0)
Private Job	13	(13.0)
If other	6	(6.0)
Total	100	(100)

Table 1 presents data about the demographic characteristics of the respondents who participated in this survey study. In this way, it was found that the respondents who participated in this study were enrolled in five various institutes and departments. That is the Department of Media & Communication Studies (20.0%), the Department of Psychology (20.0%), the Department of International Relations (20.0%), the Institute of English Language and Literature (20.0%), and the Institute of Arts and Design (20.0%) having the equal proportion of one fifth from each academic section. Second, subject to age groups, it was observed that the majority proportion (82.0%) of the respondents was 18 to 22 years old. Added in the context of mother language, it was found that the first highest proportion of about fifty percent (48.0%) of the respondents mentioned that they spoke the Urdu language; whereas, the second-highest proportion of over than a quarter (30.0%) spoke Sindhi; however, the remainder proportion (22.0%) spoke other various languages. Finally, regarding parents' occupation, the simple majority of the respondents (53.0%) said that their parents had a government job. The second-highest proportion of over a quarter (26.0%) of the respondent's parents had a personal business. Added the third-highest proportion of over one-tenth (13.0%) of the respondents mentioned that their parents had a private job. Whereas, the remaining proportion of the respondents said their parents had 'other jobs' (6.0%) and were unemployed (2.0%).

Movie Watching Preferences

Table 2: *Movie Genre*

Movie Genre	Frequency	Percent
Action	2	(2.0)
Adventure	7	(7.0)
Horror	12	(12.0)
Romance	11	(11.0)
Fantasy	3	(3.0)
Science Fiction	2	(2.0)
Comedy	18	(18.0)
Thriller	10	(10.0)
Animated	1	(1.0)
Family	4	(4.0)
All	30	(30.0)
Total	100	(100)

Table 2 has data about the preferences of the respondents regarding the genre of movies they watched more. In this way, it was seen that the proportion of over a quarter (30.0%) of the respondents mentioned that they watched movies of all genres. However, individually the first highest proportion (18.0%) was those who watched comedy movies. Then in descending order were the viewership of horror (12.0%), romance (11.0%), and thriller (10.0%) movies.

Table 3: *Movie Language*

Movie Language	Frequency	Percent (%)
English	42	(42.0)
Urdu	13	(51.0)
Tamil	1	(1.0)
Punjabi	4	(4.0)
If other	2	(2.0)
Total	100	(100)

Table 3 presents data about the languages in which movies are watched more by the respondents. Thus it was found that the simple majority of them (51.0%) watched Urdu language movies. The second-highest proportion of over two-fifths (41.0%) of the respondents said that they watched English language movies. Whereas the remaining proportion of the respondents watched the movies of Tamil (1.0%), Punjabi (4.0%), and 'other' languages (2.0%).

Table 4: *Movie Industry (continued)*

Industry	Frequency	Percent (%)
Hollywood	42	(42.0)
Bollywood	38	(38.0)

Lollywood	17	(17.0)
Tollywood	1	(1.0)
If other	2	(2.0)
Total	100	(100)

Table 4 has data about what industry movies are watched more by the Female students at the University of Sindh, Jamshoro. In this regard, it was seen that the first highest proportion of over two fifths (42.0%) of the respondents said that they watched movies made by Hollywood. The second-highest proportion of almost two-fifths (38.0%) of the respondents expressed that they watched movies made by Bollywood. Whereas, the third-highest proportion of nearly one-fifth (17.0%) of the respondents said that they watched movies made by Lollywood. However, the remaining proportion of the respondents (3.0%) watched movies made by Tollywood (1.0%), and 'other' (2.0%).

Movie Watching Patterns

Table 5: Sources to Seek Information about Movies

Movie Information Sources	Frequency	Percent (%)
Internet	50	(50.0)
Television	8	(8.0)
Magazine	1	(1.0)
YouTube	26	(26.0)
Friends	15	(15.0)
Total	100	(100)

Table 5 presents data about the sources to get information regarding movies. Thus it was observed that the first highest proportion of the size of fifty percent (50.0%) of the respondents expressed that they got information about movies from the Internet. Added for the second-highest proportion of a little over a quarter (26.0%) of the respondents, the source for receiving information regarding movies was YouTube. Whereas, the third-highest proportion of over one-tenth (15.0%) of the respondents mentioned that they got information about movies from their friends. However, for the remaining proportion (9.0%), the source for getting information about movies was television (8.0%) and magazines (1.0%).

Table 6: Movie Watching Device (continued)

Device	Frequency	Percent (%)
Television	12	(12.0)
Laptop	41	(41.0)
Mobile	43	(43.0)
DVD	1	(1.0)
Tab	1	(1.0)

If other	2	(2.0
Total	100	(100)

Table 6 presents data about what devices are used for watching movies by the Female students in the University of Sindh, Jamshoro. In this regard, it was assessed that the first highest proportion of over two-fifths (43.0%) of the respondents mentioned that they watched movies on mobile. Whereas, the second-highest proportion, sizing higher than two-fifths (41.0%) said that they watched movies on the laptop. Added the third-highest proportion of over one-tenth (12.0%) of the respondents told that they watched movies on television. Finally, the remaining proportion (4.0%) of the respondents expressed that they used DVD (1.0%), Tab (1.0%), and other devices (2.0%).

Table 7: *Movie Watching Place*

Place	Frequency	Percent (%)
Cinema	26	(26.0)
Home	67	(67.0)
Friend's home	2	(2.0)
Hostel	5	(5.0)
Total	100	(100)

Table 7 presents data about the place where the respondents watched movies. In this way, it was found that the first highest proportion of over then three-fifths (67.0%) of the respondents said that they watched movies at home. The second-highest proportion of the size of a little higher than a quarter (26.0%) of the respondents mentioned that they would go to view movies in the cinema. Whereas, the remaining proportion of 7.0% of the respondents said that they watched movies at the hostel (5.0%) and a friend’s home (2.0%).

Table 8: *Cinema Visits Monthly*

Visits Monthly	Frequency	Percent (%)
One	12	(47.0)
Twice	9	(35.0)
Thrice	5	(18.0)
Total	26	(100)

Table 8 has data regarding those respondents who watched movies in cinemas. Thus it was further known about the frequency of their cinema visits that the first highest proportion of about fifty percent (47.0%) of those respondents who watched movies in cinemas told that they visited cinema once a month. The second-highest proportion of higher than one-third (35.0%) of the respondents mentioned that they visited the cinema twice a month. However, the remaining proportion of almost one-fifth (18.0%) said that they visited the cinema thrice a month.

Table 9: *Social Context of Movie Watching*

Watching with	Frequency	Percent (%)
Family	20	(20.0)
Friends	24	(24.0)
Alone	56	(56.0)
Partner	6	(6.0)
Total	100	(100)

Table 9 presents data about the social situation surrounding the respondents while watching movies by them. Thus in this regard, it was seen that the proportion sizing higher than fifty percent (56.0%) of the respondents said that they watched movies while being alone. The second-highest proportion of almost a quarter (24.0%) expressed that they watched movies with friends; whereas, the remaining proportion, sizing one-fifth (20.0%) of the respondents, said that they watched movies with their family.

Table 10: *Purpose of Watching Movie*

Purpose	Frequency	Percent (%)
Information	6	(6.0)
Entertainment	73	(73.0)
Time pass	21	(21.0)
Total	100	(100)

Table 10 has data regarding the purpose of the movie-watching by the Female students in the University of Sindh, Jamshoro. Thus the data mentioned that the first highest proportion of almost three quarters (73.0%) of the respondents said that they watched movies for entertainment. The second-highest proportion of over one-fifth (21.0%) said that they watched movies for 'time pass.' Whereas, the remaining proportion sizing just 6.0% of the respondents expressed that their intention to watch movies was to get 'information.'

Table 11: *Watching Number of Movies Weekly*

Number of Movies	Frequency	Percent (%)
One	65	(65.0)
Two	17	(17.0)
Three	11	(11.0)
More than 3	7	(7.0)
Total	100	(100)

Table 11 presents data about the number of movies watched in a week by female students in the University of Sindh, Jamshoro. In this way, it was found that the first highest proportion of over three-fifths (65.0%) of the respondents said that they watched one movie in a week. The second-highest proportion of the respondents sizing a little less than one-fifth (17.0%) mentioned that they watched two movies in a week. Added the third-highest proportion of higher than one-tenth (11.0%) of the respondents expressed that they watched three movies in a week. However, the remaining proportion sizing just less than one-tenth (7.0%) of the respondents revealed that they watched more than three movies in a week.

Discussion and Conclusion

The purpose of this study was to assess and determine the movie-watching preferences and patterns of the female students at the University of Sindh, Jamshoro. In this way, it was found first about their demographic characteristics of the surveyed female students belonging to five various departments and institutes of the University of Sindh, Jamshoro, and age-wise; the vast majority of them were 18 to 22 years old. In Addition, the majority of them said that they spoke Urdu and Sindhi language. Finally, the simple majority of the survey participants shared that their parents were government employees.

Regarding movie watching preferences first about their choice of the genre of movies, it was found that the highest proportion that is over a quarter (30.0%) of them, mentioned that they watched the movies of all genres. Then individually, the three most popular movie genres among the female students at the University of Sindh, Jamshoro, were in descending order comedy, horror, and romance. Whereas subject to the language of the movies, it was observed that the respondents watched mostly the movies first in Urdu language and then the English language. However, in the context of the international movie industry, it was seen that they mostly watched movies made by early Hollywood and then Bollywood.

Third, in the context of movie watching patterns, it was observed that the three most favorite sources of seeking information about movies among the Female students in the University of Sindh, Jamshoro were in descending order: Internet, YouTube, and friends. Added to that, the Female students also said that the two most used devices among them to watch movies were mobile phones and laptops. As far as the place and social context for watching movies were concerned, then the Female students said that the vast majority of them watched movies at home, and then a proportion of a quarter of them watched movies at the cinema. However, the majority of the female students expressed that they preferred to watch movies alone; just a quarter of them watched movies with friends or family. Added those who watched movies in cinemas among them almost fifty percent expressed that their frequency of visiting cinemas was just once in a month. Finally, the majority of the female students said that their main purpose to watch movies is to seek entertainment rather than information or time pass. However, their frequency of watching movies was found to be one movie in a week.

Limitations of the study

The data for this study was collected from the 100 female students by purposely selected five departments of the Faculty of Social Sciences and Arts of the University of Sindh, Jamshoro. Thus the results are not so generalizable.

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